

CHANGES IN THE LIPID SPECTRUM OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE AND ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AFTER COVID-19

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Abstract. *This research is aimed to study the clinical course of chronic heart failure (CHF) and arterial hypertension, their specific characteristics, and changes in lipid profile in the post-COVID-19 period. 90 patients with CHF and arterial hypertension (stage II-III) were studied. The first group included 55 patients with CHF and arterial hypertension (stage II-III) who had undergone COVID-19. The second group consisted of 35 patients with the same diagnosis, but who had not contracted COVID-19, according to their medical history and laboratory indicators. All patients underwent standard examinations and were re-examined after six months, and the results were compared. The difference in total cholesterol levels between the main group and the control group at the initial examination was 21.2% ($p < 0.01$) for patients of stage II of CHF, and 22.4% ($p < 0.01$) for patients of stage III of CHF. The triglyceride level difference was 11.6% ($p < 0.05$) for patients of stage II of CHF, and 12.4% ($p < 0.05$) for patients of stage III of CHF. The difference in the levels of low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) was 22.8% ($p < 0.01$) for patients of stage II of CHF, and 24.6% ($p < 0.01$) for patients of stage III of CHF. The difference in high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C) was 16.8% ($p < 0.01$) for patients of stage II of CHF, and 18.6% ($p < 0.01$) for patients of stage III of CHF. The results were consistent and statistically significant.*

Keywords: *chronic heart failure, post-COVID-19 period, lipid spectrum, arterial hypertension.*

Relevance of the Topic: It is well known that viral infections lead to a strong local inflammation of the blood vessel walls and systemic inflammatory responses, which can result in acute coronary syndrome, arrhythmias, heart failure decompensation, and thromboembolic complications. COVID-19 infection can lead to these complications and worsen the course of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) as well as contribute to the development of life-threatening additional complications [1,4,6]. The complications that may occur in patients with chronic heart failure (CHF) during the COVID-19 period, the short- and long-term changes in the cardiovascular system (CVS), as well as the stages of the severity and clinical course of CHF, have not been fully studied. The SARS-CoV-2 virus directly damages cardiomyocytes, leading to decompensation of CHF, shock states, and sudden coronary events [2,7]. Recent studies have shown that COVID-19 increases the risk of arrhythmias in patients with CVD. Among the possible arrhythmias, atrial fibrillation (AF), supraventricular and ventricular extrasystoles, ventricular tachycardia (VT), and bradyarrhythmias are common.

The main mechanisms of arrhythmogenesis during the acute phase of infection include myocardial damage (necrosis, apoptosis, inflammation, ischemia), ion imbalance, sympathetic nervous system activation, and hypoxemia [3,5].

Research Objective: To study the peculiarities of the clinical course of chronic heart failure (CHF) and arterial hypertension (AH) in patients with stable angina pectoris of ischemic heart disease (IHD) stage II and III, and lipid spectrum changes during the post-COVID-19 period.

Materials and Methods: The study involved 90 patients with IHD, stable angina pectoris (stage II and III), complicated by chronic heart failure (CHF) stage II and III, treated at the multi-disciplinary clinic of Tashkent Medical Academy (TMA). The first group consisted of 55 patients who had contracted COVID-19 and had IHD and CHF stage II-III. The time interval for COVID-19 in this group was 4 ± 0.43 months. The second group consisted of 35 patients with IHD but no history of COVID-19. All patients underwent the following tests: assessment of complaints, collection of medical history, examination of objective status, heart rate (HR), pulse (P), blood pressure, and cardiology tests: complete blood count, urinalysis, coagulation profile, lipid spectrum, echocardiography, and Holter ECG monitoring.

The Holter ECG (24-hour monitoring) was analyzed to study the heart rhythm and conduction disturbances, average heart rate per minute, and the diurnal and nocturnal average values of heart contractions, the circadian index, and the QT interval. All patients were tested for COVID-19 using PCR and IgG for SARS-CoV-2 in the blood. The average age of the first group was 64.2 ± 9.3 years, and the second group was 67 ± 11.1 years. The clinical condition of the patients was assessed using the SHOKS scale (Maryeev, 2000) and quality of life using the Minnesota questionnaire. These patients were re-examined after six months.

Patients with acute cerebrovascular disease, severe diabetes, acute exacerbations of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, and complex types of arrhythmia were excluded from the study.

Results and Discussion: The patients with IHD/CHF were divided into two groups based on their medical history of COVID-19 infection.

One group consisted of patients who had undergone COVID-19 within the last 6 months, and the second group consisted of patients who had not contracted COVID-19. The first group had an average age of 64.2 ± 9.3 years, and the second group had an average age of 67 ± 11.1 years. These patients were re-examined after 6 months, during which time they were continuously taking statins, antiplatelet drugs, and ACE inhibitors. The compliance with medication intake was monitored through phone calls and local healthcare providers (as indicated in Table 1).

The results of the study were compared between the two groups, and all patients were assessed with standard tests during follow-up. A total of 54 patients from the first group and 34 patients from the control group participated in the re-examination.

One patient from the first group refused hospitalization, and one patient from the control group was excluded due to COVID-19 infection. The re-examination was conducted after 6 months, with an average follow-up period of 7 ± 0.15 months for the main group and 7 ± 0.2 months for the control group.

All 90 patients examined were diagnosed with stage III hypertension. According to the initial assessment, the percentage distribution of arterial hypertension (AH) levels in Group 1 patients was as follows: level 1 - 22.7%, level 2 - 36.4%, and level 3 - 40.9%. In Group 2, the percentages were 40% for grade 1, 36% for grade 2, and 24% for grade 3. Among Group 1 patients who had experienced COVID-19, level 3 of AH was predominant. In contrast, level 2 of AH was more prevalent in Group 2 (Figure 1.1).

Table 1. General Characteristics of the Examined Patients at the Initial and 6-Month Follow-Up Examinations

Indicator	1 st group n=55 (M±m)	Group 1 (after 6 months) n=54 (M±m)	2 nd group n=35 (M±m)	Group 2 n=34 (after 6 months) (M±m)
Age	64,2±9,3	64,1±9,2	67,0±11,1	67,0±9,1
Male/ female	30/25 (54,5%/45,5 %)	29/25 (53,5%/46,5 %)	18/17 (52%/48%)	17/17 (50%/50%)
IHD. Stable angina pectoris	55 (100%)	54 (100%)	35 (100%)	34 (100%)
High blood pressure	55 (100%)	54 (100%)	35 (100%)	34 (100%)
Arterial hypertension				
Level I	12 (22%)	25 (46,5%)	14 (40%)	25 (75%)
Level II	20 (36,4%)	18 (32,6%)	13 (36%)	9 (25%)
Level III	23 (40,9%)	11 (20,1%)	8 (24%)	0
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	24 (43,5%)	24 (43,5%)	14 (40%)	14 (40%)
TMI, kg/m ²	32,1±0,78	32,1±0,78	28,1±1,94	28,1±1,94
Extra weight	20 (36,7)	16 (36,7)	14 (40%)	14 (40%)
Overweightness	32 (59,1%)	32 (59,1%)	14 (40%)	14 (40%)
Level I	15 (46,1%)	15 (46,1%)	17 (50%)	17 (50%)
Level II	10(30,8%)	10(30,8%)	10 (30%)	10 (30%)
Level III	7(23,1%)	7(23,1%)	7 (20%)	7 (20%)
SyuYe				
According to FS II NYHA	26 (47,73%)	26 (48,1%)	18(52%)	17(50%)
According to FS III NYHA	29(52,2%)	28(51,9%)	17(48%)	17(50%)

Despite all patients regularly taking prescribed medications, follow-up examinations revealed episodes of elevated blood pressure among patients in the main group with a history of COVID-19 (observed in 38% of these patients). A comparison of blood pressure levels during the follow-up showed that level 3 of arterial hypertension in the main group had decreased by 50.2% compared to initial results. However, achieving full normotension remained low. In the control group, no cases of level 3 of arterial hypertension were identified during the follow-up, likely due to the selection of appropriate antihypertensive therapy (Table 1.1).

Laboratory results from the initial examination indicated the following changes in the lipid profile of patients:

In the main and control groups, the difference in total cholesterol levels was 21.2% ($p<0.01$) for patients with CVD FS II and 22.4% ($p<0.01$) for patients with CVD FS III.

The difference in triglyceride levels was 11.6% ($p<0.05$) for patients with CVD FS II and 12.4% ($p<0.05$) for those with CVD FS III.

The difference in LDL-C levels was 22.8% ($p < 0.01$) for CVD FS II patients and 24.6% ($p < 0.01$) for CVD FS III patients.

The difference in HDL-C levels was 16.8% ($p < 0.01$) for CVD FS II patients and 18.6% ($p < 0.01$) for CVD FS III patients.

Figure 1.1. Distribution of arterial hypertension levels based on the initial results of the examined patients.

The statistical significance of these results was confirmed. Based on the lipid profile analysis, patients in the main group with a history of COVID-19 exhibited elevated levels of lipids associated with an increased risk of atherosclerosis. All patients were taking statins at the time of the lipid profile examination (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2. Changes in the lipid profile of patients

Indicators	Groups of patients	Group1	Group 2	R
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 4,3±0,17	n=18; 3,5±0,14	<0,01
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 4,9±0,18	n=17; 4,1±0,2	<0,01
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 1,7±0,13	n=18; 1,3±0,19	<0,05
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 1,8±0,16	n=17; 1,4±0,14	<0,05
XM-PZLP (mmol/l)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 3,9±0,17	n=18; 2,2±0,13	<0,01
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 4,2±0,17	n=17; 2,5±0,14	<0,01
XM-YuZLP (mmol/l)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 0,9±0,08	n=18; 1,2±0,06	<0,01
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 0,8±0,05	n=17; 1,1±0,09	<0,01

After six months, an analysis of the lipid profile of patients yielded the following results: a significant difference was observed in the levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL-C, while no significant difference was found in HDL-C levels. In this context, patients in Group 1

showed dynamic improvement; however, their levels remained higher compared to those in the control group who had not contracted COVID-19. These findings suggest that dyslipidemic changes persist for an extended period in patients who have had COVID-19.

Table 1.3. Changes in the lipid profile of patients during the follow-up examination

Indicators	Groups of patients	Group 1		Group 2	
		Initial examination	After 6 months	Initial examination	After 6 months
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 4,3±0,17	n=26 3,5±0,12*	n=18; 3,5±0,14	n=17 2,9±0,14*
	SyuYe FS III	n=29; 4,9±0,18	n=29 3,91±0,18*	n=17; 4,1±0,2	n=17 3,25±0,2*
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 1,7±0,13	n=26; 1,4±0,12*	n=18; 1,3±0,19	n=17; 1,07±0,11*
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 1,8±0,16	n=29; 1,5±0,11*	n=17; 1,4±0,14	n=17; 1,18±0,1*
XM-PZLP (mmol/l)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 3,9±0,17	n=26; 2,8±0,1*	n=18; 2,2±0,13	n=17; 1,8±0,1*
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 4,2±0,17	n=29; 3,4±0,12*	n=17; 2,5±0,14	n=17; 2,0±0,11*
XM-YuZLP (mmol/l)	SYuYe FS II	n=26; 0,9±0,08	n=26; 1,1±0,1*	n=18; 1,2±0,06	n=17; 1,22±0,08
	SYuYe FS III	n=29; 0,8±0,05	n=29; 1,1±0,05*	n=17; 1,1±0,09	n=17; 1,19±0,07

* p<0,05;

Conclusion

Based on the examination results of patients in the main group, differences in blood pressure levels were identified, and these findings were consistent during the follow-up examination. It was concluded that COVID-19 infection worsened the clinical condition of these patients and complicated their treatment, as well as increased the risk of developing resistant hypertension (RH). Analyzing the lipid profile results also confirmed that COVID-19 infection contributed to dyslipidemia, and this condition persisted 5-9 months after the infection. Consequently, an increase in cardiovascular events and hospitalization rates was predicted for these patients. Based on these results, it is recommended to develop early rehabilitation strategies for patients who have contracted COVID-19 and to re-optimize antihypertensive and hypolipidemic treatment.

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